

THE DAILY ECONOMIC CHALLENGES OF COBBLER FAMILIES IN RANGPUR CITY, BANGLADESH

Md. Sobur Hossain^{1,*}, Nishat Tasnim², Md. Zahidul Islam³, Rusaid Ahmed⁴

^{1,2}Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Science, Begum Rokeya University, Rangpur, 5400, Bangladesh

³Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Science, University of Dhaka, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh

⁴Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Faculty of Social Science, Begum Rokeya University, Rangpur, 5400, Bangladesh

*Corresponding author, soc1915034brur@gmail.com

Received Date: 28/07/2024

Accepted Date: 30/11/2024

Published Date: 30/12/2024

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the daily economic challenges faced by cobbler families in Rangpur City. The study employed a qualitative approach, utilizing purposive sampling, to conduct in-depth interviews with 20 participants. The data were analyzed using a thematic framework. The findings indicate that cobblers' daily income ranged from Tk 300 to Tk 400. Education, transportation, elderly care, childcare, and daily necessities are the primary expenditures of cobblers, which place a substantial burden on their limited income. The seasonality of income results in considerable variation, as it is higher during festivals and winters, and lower during monsoons and summers. Furthermore, cobblers depend on loans from banks and non-government organizations (NGOs) to finance wedding expenses, business investments, housing, livestock, social assistance, education, home renovations, and medical expenses.

Keywords: cobbler families; medical expenses; non-government organizations; qualitative approach; rangpur city.

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is a densely populated developing country in Southern Asia (Etzold & Mallick, 2015). Approximately 77% of the population lives in rural areas, with 80% being dependent on agriculture (Mohajan, 2013). According to the Asian Development Bank (2010), informal employment accounted for 89% of the total jobs in the labor market in Bangladesh based on a labor force survey conducted in 2010. Notably, 77% of these jobs were in informal production units, mainly consisting of unpaid family workers and daily wage workers, across both the agricultural and non-agricultural sectors. Furthermore, more than 40% of the country's Gross Value Added (GVA) in 2010 came from the informal sector, with significant contributions from agriculture, fisheries, trade, and relatively less capital-intensive industries (Yasin, 2022). The informal sector, which includes cottage, micro, small, and medium enterprises as well as cobbling, operates closest to local communities and plays a crucial role in creating local jobs, especially for women and youth in Bangladesh (Dallakoti, 2024).

Bangladesh, like India and Pakistan, is mainly Muslim, but has significant ethnic and religious diversity. Approximately 10% of the population is Hindu, with a substantial portion hailing from the lower levels of the Hindu caste hierarchy known as “Dalit” (Guhathakurta & Begum, 2022). The term “Dalit” refers to lower castes facing marginalization and discrimination, often compelled to work in deplorable conditions for minimal compensation (Banglapedia, 2021). Among the estimated 3.5 to 5.5 million “Dalits” in Bangladesh (International Dalit Solidarity Network, 2024; Mondal, 2015), cobblers—referred to as “Muchi” or “Rishi”—form a significant and particularly disadvantaged group.

Cobblers, experts in working with leather, belong to a marginalized community (Pal, 2011). They sew, cut, dye, patch, sand, polish, seal, shine, and mend during workdays (History of the Cobbler, n.d.). Within the “Muchi” community are two sects: Robidas, who produce new leather items, and Haridas, who repair colors and polish old shoes and other leather products (Saha & Paul, 2003). Their income is derived solely from repairing footwear and shoe-shining (Pandey & Vats, 2020). Despite their vital role, cobblers' professions are often viewed with little financial gain and prestige (Becker, 2012).

The cobbler community faces severe social, economic, political, and cultural disadvantages, struggling daily to make ends meet. This community exemplifies a typical enterprise in the traditional informal sector—characterized by small-scale, labor-intensive operations, lower productivity, and limited use of technology (Bairagya, 2010). Their earnings are typically skewed towards the lower end of the income distribution (Hamid & Jain, 2023), highlighting the scale of their economic challenges.

The dire economic situation of cobbler communities is particularly acute in urban areas, where life can be harsh and brutal (Saha & Paul, 2003). Their earnings are often inadequate, leading to hunger and lacking essential needs such as food, clothing, shelter, education, and healthcare (Halder & Urey, 2003; Aktar & Halder, 2023). The existing literature reveals that cobblers are generally not well-off, which compels them to live from hand-to-mouth.

Unlike cobbler communities in Dhaka or Chittagong, where high demand drives specialization, cobblers in Rangpur City rely heavily on localized networks and traditional craftsmanship, reflecting their socio-economic struggles and adaptive strategies in a less industrialized urban environment.

Despite the significant contribution of informal laborers to Bangladesh's economy, the cobbler community has garnered minimal academic focus, especially in mid-tier cities such as Rangpur. While existing studies largely focus on large urban hubs, forgetting the distinctive dynamics of smaller cities, no significant research has been undertaken on the socio-economic situations of cobblers in Rangpur. This research intends to address this gap by offering a deeper understanding of the socio-economic issues encountered by the cobbler community in Rangpur City.

Therefore, the study addresses the following objectives: (1) to determine the daily income level of cobbler families, (2) to identify the cobbler households' primary sources of expenditure, (3) to explore the impact of seasonal variations on the economic stability of cobbler families, and (4) to investigate credit facilities and purpose of taking loans among cobbler families.

METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN

The study employed a qualitative method to explore the economic challenges faced by the cobbler community in Rangpur, Bangladesh. This approach enabled the researchers to capture the participants' experiences of daily economic challenges and broader life difficulties. Yin (2003) asserts that qualitative research emphasizes authentic representations of participants' perspectives and experiences. In this case, the study aims to provide a deeper understanding of the lives of cobblers in Rangpur. It also offers an opportunity to enhance comprehension of the economic challenges faced by this marginalized community.

STUDY AREA

The research was conducted in the Park Mor, Lalbagh, Jahaj-Company, Bank Mor, Modern, Chokbazar, Shapla, Bus Terminal, Medical Mor, Darshana, and Police Lines areas of Rangpur city, located in northern Bangladesh. These areas are home to 1,000 cobblers. The cobblers, a minority community in the town, have traditionally been involved in the profession of cobblers. This occupation serves as a vital source of income for their families, and many have been engaged in this work for generations. We selected Rangpur City for this study because the researchers are residents of the area and have prior familiarity with its people, which positively influenced the research process. This familiarity facilitated the establishment of a strong rapport with the cobbler community in Rangpur. Moreover, no prior studies have been conducted on the cobbler community in Rangpur, making this research both unique and significant.

Figure 1: Study Area Location

PARTICIPANTS AND SAMPLING

The study employed a purposive sampling strategy. Palinkas et al. (2015) and Kelly et al. (2010) observed that researchers often utilize purposive sampling techniques to identify individuals who can provide relevant and valuable insights, optimizing limited research resources. This study selected 20 participants from the cobbler community in Rangpur city. They represent a unique aspect of the city's character. The participants were all male, as women in the town typically engaged in domestic work. All were married but lacked formal education, with most only able to sign their names. All participants were also Hindu. Participants were distributed across different age groups: five (05) participants aged 20-30, ten (04) participants aged 31-40, twelve (03) participants aged 41-50, ten (06) participants aged 51-60, and three (02) participants over 60.

The 20 participants were interviewed in depth. According to Boyce & Neale (2006), in-depth interviews are a qualitative research method involving one-on-one, detailed interviews with a few participants to explore their views on a particular concept, program, or situation. Rutledge and Hogg (2020) argue that this approach often complements other data, such as outcome measures, enabling a deeper understanding of the research phenomenon and its underlying causes.

Table 1. Participants Sampling

NAME OF THE AREAS	SAMPLING SIZE
Park-Mor	02
Lalbagh	03
Jahaj-Company	02
Banker-Mor	01
Modern	01
Chokbazar	01
Shapla	01
Bus-Terminal	02
Medical-Mor	02
Darshana	02
Police-lines	03
Total	20

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Three researchers participated in the data collection, partitioning the data into two categories. An open-ended questionnaire was developed before data collection. Open-ended questions allow respondents to answer in their own words without being guided by predefined options (Popping, 2015). All questionnaires and data collection activities were conducted in Bengali, as respondents could express their feelings and opinions most freely in their native language. The participants, all actively engaged in the cobbler profession, typically set up at roadside or street intersections daily. The researchers documented their observations and recorded audio to capture comprehensive information during the data collection. The process took place over two days. Data was collected from the Park-Mor, Lalbagh, Jahaj-Company, Bank-Mor, and Modern area on the first day. On the second day, data was gathered from Chokbazar, Shapla, the Bus Terminal, Medical-Mor, Darshana, and Police Lines areas. A pilot study was conducted to confirm the cobblers' positions. A pilot study

is a smaller-scale preliminary investigation that aids in planning, refining, and modifying the main study (Arnold et al., 2009; Thabane et al., 2010). After completing data collection, the researchers expressed their gratitude to the respondents.

DATA ANALYSIS

We transcribed the captured data before analysis. Since the participants were Bengali speakers, the textual data was translated into English and verified accurately through cross-checking. We categorized the translated data by identifying key themes using a thematic framework, which was determined after a thorough review. Thematic analysis (TA) was applied to examine, identify, and illustrate the patterns of significance, or 'themes, within the data (Joffe, 2011). Furthermore, thematic analyses are conducive to identifying repeated ideas or themes in a textual data set (Guest et al., 2012).

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

All respondents participated in a pre-interview briefing about the purpose of the study and the use of audio recorders. Thus, no personally identifiable information was gathered during the study, and all the information gathered was stored securely to prevent participant identification. Ethical considerations were strictly upheld throughout the study. After the data were interpreted and analyzed, all collected data were deleted to prevent potential information leakage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We identified themes based on the study objectives. From the first objective, three themes emerged: (1) income range and earnings, (2) income fluctuation, and (3) family contribution and combined income. From the Second objective, five emerged: (1) daily essentials, (2) education, (3) transportation, (4) elderly care, and (5) childcare. From the third (3) objective, three (3) themes emerged: (1) festival season, (2) winter season, and (3) summer and monsoon season. Finally, from the fourth (4) objective, eight (8) themes emerged: (1) marriage expenses, (2) business investments, (3) housing, (4) livestock, (5) social support, (6) education, (7) home renovation, and (8) medical expenses.

DAILY EARNING LEVELS OF COBBLER FAMILIES

The study found that the only source of income for cobblers' families is the cobbling profession, but the income is not identical for everyone.

Five (5) respondents reported a daily income of TK 300-350. They generate a total of 300 to 350 TK from morning to nightfall. All of them expressed the same sentiment.

"I earn TK 300-350 by selling shoe polish, sewing bags, and selling shoes from morning to evening." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

Eight (8) respondents said their daily income ranges from 350 to 400 TK; however, this revenue is not consistently available and fluctuates sometimes.

"I make an average of Rs 350 to 400 daily, albeit this amount varies daily." (Face-to-Face Interview, 25 August 2024)

Two (2) respondents said that their income fluctuates between 200 and 300 TK.

"I earn between 200 to 300 TK every day. "(Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

Two (2) respondents said their daily income ranges from 300 to 400; however, they must try to get it. After spending the whole day in the sun by the roadside, the family successfully obtains their desires.

"I earn between 300 to 400 TK daily." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

One (1) responder said my wife and I have a TK 500-600 salary.

"I am a cobbler, while my wife manufactures cement bags at home, resulting in a daily family income of TK 500-600." (Face-to-Face Interview, 25 August 2024)

MAJOR EXPENSES OF COBBLER HOUSEHOLDS

The study found that respondents' households face significant financial challenges. Their income is primarily consumed by daily necessities, limiting their ability to save for the future. Their expenditures encompass daily essentials, education for their children, transportation, and medical expenses.

DAILY ESSENTIALS

All respondents stated that their main expense is to buy everyday items. Most of what they earn goes to buy food every day. The respondents cited the high price of essential commodities as the reason for the increase in the cost. One of the respondents said:

"My electricity bill and food expenses significantly exceed my income. No matter how much money I earn, I exhaust myself before I arrive home because I need to buy daily necessities. If I grapple with any economic crisis, I do not have any savings, which will help me escape the peril." (in-depth interview, 25 August 2024)

EDUCATION

All respondents reported spending their children's school fees, textbooks, food, and travel expenses together. For example, one of the respondents said:

"Fortunately, I have two sons and a daughter who attend school regularly. I need to pay their school fees, buy papers and books, and give them money to take snacks during their leisure time. So, my highest expense is food, followed by educational costs." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

TRANSPORTATION

Six (6) respondents said they commute daily from village to town to work as cobblers. In that case, they have to pay a significant amount of fare. The daily fare represents one side of their expenses. For example, one of the respondents said:

"I commute to other Upazilas daily, which costs me 40–50 TK as a bus and rickshaw fare." (Face-to-Face Interview, 25 August 2024)

ELDERLY CARE

Twelve (12) respondents reported that they had to spend a month buying medicines for elderly parents. The elderly parents need medicines regularly due to various diseases and physical problems, they said. One of the respondents said:

“My mother is of advanced age. She requires a minimum of 2000 TK equivalent medicine every 30 days.” (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

CHILDCARE

Five (6) respondents said that another area of their spending is the care of their children. It is expensive for them to take the children to the doctor, diapers, and food. One of them said:

“My daughter is three. She needs a lot of medicines and diapers, which forces me to borrow money for many months.” (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

IMPACT OF SEASONAL VARIATIONS ON THE ECONOMIC STABILITY

Participants' income fluctuates significantly with the seasons, showing marked increases during festivals and colder months while declining during the monsoon and summer seasons.

Table 2. Seasonal Income Fluctuations of Cobblers in Bangladesh

Seasons	Income Range (TK)	Key Observations
Eid	1500–2000	Highest income due to increased demand for shoe polishing and repair, lasting 4–5 days.
Puja	500–600	Moderate income boost during the largest Hindu festival; less pronounced than Eid.
Winter	600–700	Increased shoe usage leads to a steady demand for polishing services.
Monsoon	150–200	Lowest income; reduced shoe usage due to fear of spoilage from rain.
Summer	150–200	Low income: fewer people wear leather shoes due to the heat.
General (Non-peak)	300–500	Daily income during regular periods without significant seasonal or festival impacts.

FESTIVAL SEASONS

The participants reported that during significant festivals like Eid (the biggest religious festival for Muslims) and Puja (the biggest religious festival for Hindus), cobblers experience a surge in income. As Bangladesh is predominantly Muslim, Eid brings substantial business, with affluent customers seeking superior-quality shoe polishing and the less affluent repairing and sewing their existing shoes. This busy period lasts 4-5 days before the festival, boosting their daily income to between 1500 and 2000 TK.

“While I generally have much spare time daily and earn 300-500 TK, I become swamped during Eid, with a soaring income of 1500 to 2000 TK daily.” (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

Similarly, during Puja, the most significant Hindu festival, respondents see an income increase, although less pronounced than during Eid, typically earning around 500–600 TK daily.

“Every year, I earn 500–600 TK during Puja, but not as much as in winter and Eid.” (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

WINTER SEASON

The study's respondents said that Winter also provides increased income opportunities as people wear stylish shoes more frequently, requiring regular polishing. This seasonal demand results in daily earnings rising to 600–700 TK.

“Due to the excessive use of shoes in winter, our income rises significantly from 300–500 TK to 700 TK.” (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

MONSOON AND SUMMER SEASON

Conversely, the monsoon and summer seasons are challenging for respondents' families. During the rainy season, the fear of leather shoe spoilage reduces the use of such footwear, while the intense heat of summer leads to fewer people wearing shoes. Consequently, their income can drop to as low as 150–200 TK daily.

“During the rainy season and scorching hot days, I merely earn 150–200 TK, which is much lower income than any other time of the year, as very few people wear leather shoes and sandals during these seasons. So, my workload is minimal.” (Face-to-Face Interview, 25 August 2024)

CREDIT FACILITIES AND PURPOSE OF TAKING LOANS

The research revealed that credit facilities are available, and the participating households primarily obtain credit from banks and NGOs rather than from informal sources like family, friends, or moneylenders. “Our relatives, friends, and creditors are unwilling to offer us financial assistance.” The participants obtained loans from Grameen Bank, ASA Foundation, WAVE Foundation, TMSS, and BRAC NGOs. These loans have been instrumental in addressing their diverse financial requirements.

MARRIAGE EXPENSES

Many cobblers take loans for their daughters' marriages, especially in the Hindu community, where substantial expenses for jewelry and dowries are required; interviewees indicated that they were required to secure loans for their daughter's weddings. The expense of marriage among the Hindu community is reportedly more than that of other religions. Jewellery is a fundamental component for Hindus during a daughter's wedding. Moreover, they asserted that the dowry and two meals for the bridegroom escalated the wedding expenses. It was revealed that they were compelled to get loans.

"I expended TK 4 lakh on my daughter's nuptials. I am financially disadvantaged; in addition to providing dowry and jewelry, I lack the funds to support the bridegroom. However, I was compelled to arrange my daughter's marriage, prompting me to secure a loan of Tk 2 lakh from the Grameen Bank." (Face-to-Face Interview, 25 August 2024)

BUSINESS

All the participants said that they had acquired loans for commercial purposes. Owing to a lack of business capital, they secured loans to sustain their enterprises. They use this financing to operate leather, procure shoe-making raw materials, and manage tiny shoe shops.

"I procure a loan of Tk 30,000 from Grameen Bank to acquire raw materials for my firm, including shoe ink, animal hide, and shoe manufacturing supplies." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

HOUSING

Four (4) individuals said they previously resided in rented accommodations but have now acquired land and constructed a house. However, they fail to repay this amount. A respondent stated:

"I possess neither land nor property. I formerly resided in a rental property; however, I have since purchased land and constructed a modest tin house, for which I secured a loan of 70,000 from BRAC NGO." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

LIVESTOCK

Two (2) respondents indicated that they purchased cows on credit. They said that they would profit by purchasing cows and repaying the debt with dividends. Due to the elevated market prices for cattle, they may achieve greater profit margins.

"I procured a cow using a loan of Rs 50,000 from Wave Foundation NGO. The profit to be realized upon repaying this debt following the sale of the cow." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

FAMILY SUPPORT

All respondents indicated that during the rainy season, when revenue diminishes, loans assist households in covering daily and critical expenses. During the rainy season, individuals refrain from wearing leather shoes, which results in a substantial decline in their income.

"I have secured a loan of Rs 2 lakh. Due to my significantly reduced income during the rainy season, the family's expenditures are not influenced by elevated prices during this period." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

EDUCATION

Two (2) respondents indicated that they secured loans to cover their children's examination fees. Their children participated in the 2024 SSC (Secondary School Certificate) examination. He secured a loan to finance the examination.

"I obtained a loan of Rs 10,000 from TMSS to pay my son's SSC examination fees." (Face-to-Face Interview, 25 August 2024)

HOME RENOVATION

One (1) respondent indicated that during the rainy season, his tin stove ruptured because of water exposure, prompting him to repair the house. He secured a loan of Rs 10,000 to refurbish the residence.

"Water is seeping from the roof. I obtained a loan from Asha NGO to purchase home tins." (Face-to-Face Interview, 26 August 2024)

MEDICAL EXPENSES

Three (3) respondents indicated that their elderly parents had acquired loans to cover medical expenditures. When their parents were unwell and had financial resources at home, no one was willing to assist them, prompting them to secure a loan to cover medical expenditures.

"My father was very ill. I took a loan of TK 50,000 from Grameen Bank and got my father treated as if no one had lent money despite telling many people." (Face-to-Face Interview, 25 August 2024)

Our study aims to explore the primary sources of daily familial earnings, household spending patterns, income variations throughout the year, accessibility to credit, and the purpose of borrowing within cobbler families in Rangpur. The findings revealed that the cobbler profession remains the primary source of income for most families. Daily-earnings typically range from Tk 300 to 350, which aligns with previous studies. For example, Farhat (2020) and Saha and Paul (2003) reported that the average daily income of cobblers was approximately Tk 350. However, Mondal (2015) suggests a broader income range of Tk 250–500, reflecting potential regional or methodological differences. Comparatively, cobbler families in Pune, India, earn approximately Rs 170 daily, according to Hamid & Jain (2023), while those in Tripura, India, have an average daily income of Rs 248 (Tribal Research & Cultural Institute, Tripura, 2020). Despite these variations, income levels across these regions underscore the persistent economic challenges faced by cobbler communities. Notably, most cobbler families in

Bangladesh earn less than \$50 per month, with only a few surpassing \$75, as highlighted by Toppo et al. (2016). This financial strain is further exacerbated when families without supplementary income sources are considered.

This study also demonstrates the spending patterns of cobbler families, where most of their daily income is allocated to essential food items. This finding is consistent with the observations of Aktar and Halder (2023), who noted that most households spend between Tk 3,001 and Tk 5,000 monthly on food, with an average expenditure of Tk 3,910. Education is the second most significant financial burden, with monthly expenses ranging from Tk 450 to Tk 500, averaging around Tk 390 (Aktar & Halder, 2023). This highlights the dual challenge of maintaining basic living standards and striving to invest in the future through education.

A critical aspect of cobbler family income is its fluctuation due to seasonal variation. During religious festivals like Eid and Puja, earnings can increase significantly, ranging from Tk 1,500 to 2,000 during Eid and Tk 500 to 600 during Puja. Winter also brings higher earnings between Tk 400 and Tk 500 daily. These periods of increased income are crucial for the financial survival of cobbler families as they often compensate for leaner times. However, during the monsoon season, income drops sharply because of transportation difficulties and reduced customer demand. Kamal et al. (2010) reported that daily earnings could plummet to as low as Tk 30 to 40 during heavy rains, with some cobblers earning nothing. Seasonal vulnerability is a significant factor contributing to the economic instability of cobbler families. Hamid and Jain (2023) similarly observed income declines during high-temperature and rainy periods in Pune, India, suggesting a broader trend of seasonal income fluctuation in this profession.

The study also reveals that all cobbler households in Rangpur have access to credit with loans provided by both governmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). Institutions such as ADDIN Somiti, BRAC, and the Grameen Bank play a pivotal role in supporting these communities, as noted by Martin et al. (2020). Despite this access to credit, cobbler families are heavily indebted, often borrowing sums ranging from Tk 30,000 to Tk 2 lakhs. The necessity of these loans stems from the fact that their expenditures often exceed their income, leading to a cycle of debt that is difficult to break. The History of the Cobbler community shows a deep-rooted reliance on debt as a means of survival (History of the Cobbler n.d.).

This study enriches the academic literature by providing an informal nuanced and detailed discussion of the urban cobbler of Rangpur. It provides valuable insights into the occupational practices and challenges of the cobbler community, which can be helpful in formulating policies to improve the livelihoods of these informal workers. Moreover, by shedding light on the economic and social contributions of cobbler communities, this study aligns with global efforts to drive sustainable urban development and reduce inequalities.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study thoroughly analyzes the economic difficulties encountered by cobbler families. However, it is important to recognize the limitations of this study. The study sample consisted only of cobblers who worked in roadside or crossroad vocations within the local community. Owing to the intense heat, obtaining information from cobblers over a prolonged period is difficult. Female participants were excluded from the study. Therefore, studies typically exhibit a certain level of gender bias. The availability of comprehensive data may be restricted when respondents focus on their employment in most of the interviews. Some individuals had such a profound literacy deficiency, making it difficult to obtain information from them. Moreover, there is a scarcity of studies on this topic. Nevertheless, this comprehensive study has

undoubtedly played a crucial role in uncovering several issues that cobblers encounter daily, and we hope this study could serve as a reference for further research.

FUTURE DIRECTION FOR RESEARCH

This study thoroughly analyzes the economic difficulties and challenges faced by the cobbler community in Rangpur, highlighting the severe financial instability and indebtedness that define their everyday lives. Their families' financial circumstances are fragile, and they are encumbered by debt for many reasons to maintain their livelihoods. While this research offers extensive insights into these obstacles, more unresolved issues remain, especially concerning the impact of poverty on the mental health of cobblers. Understanding the impact of poverty on mental health and economic issues is essential. The mental health of the cobbler community is undermined by economic challenges, which affect their everyday existence and psychological well-being. Future studies are crucial for examining the psychological effects of poverty. This will aid them in understanding the magnitude of their financial challenges while providing a realistic evaluation of the deterioration in their mental health. This study has the potential to substantially improve the socio-economic development and general quality of life of the population. Innovative methodologies may be established by analyzing the intricate interplay between economic conditions and mental health. This will provide concrete enhancements to their psychological well-being and financial stability.

IMPLICATION OF THE FINDINGS

This study may provide a solid basis for further research into the economic challenges of the Cobbler community, representing one of its principal contributions. This research highlights the Cobbler family's financial difficulties and their impact on their lives, illustrating that economic stability is the essential cornerstone of every community. Individuals' lives become too tricky when the framework is insufficient. The results of this study are particularly significant for policymakers as they may influence their decision-making processes. The research findings suggest that creating diverse labor markets might enhance societal welfare by providing job opportunities in various professions. This will improve their quality of life and increase their income. Research can also enhance public awareness in this regard. The government may obtain support for essential policy measures by concentrating on the socioeconomic circumstances of cobblers. Collaborating with the underprivileged may mitigate their distress and improve their quality of life, provided that the government and other social organizations enact appropriate steps.

CONCLUSION

A cobbler's family's daily income is insufficient to cover their basic needs, leaving little room for savings. Financial commitments burden many people, and they are always obsessed with finding ways to support themselves. They regard their work as an unremitting pursuit, relentlessly toiling from dawn to dusk to defray their family's expenses. The current increase in cost has worsened people's difficulties. They lack financial resources and social resources. They encounter social censure that impedes their capacity to obtain loans. Overall, governments must take practical steps to improve the socioeconomic situation of cobblers. Collective efforts from NGOs, banks, and charity organizations must aim to help cobblers financially lead comfortable lifestyles.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am deeply indebted to the researchers of this study, Miss Nishat Tasnim, Department of Sociology, Begum Rokeya University, Rangpur; Mr. Zahidul Islam, Department of Sociology, University of Dhaka; and Mr. Rusaid Ahmed, Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Begum Rokeya University, Rangpur for their remarkable contribution to the smooth conduct of this research. They have assisted me the most in data gathering, data analysis, writing, and editing this study, and have equally contributed to this research. I also express my gratitude to the members of the cobbler community who aided us with the information in this research. Furthermore, I would like to extend my appreciation to anonymous reviewers, whose invaluable contributions have facilitated the publication of this paper.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Arnold, D. M., Burns, K. E., Adhikari, N. K., Kho, M. E., Meade, M. O., & Cook, D. J. (2009). The design and interpretation of pilot trials in clinical research in critical care. *Critical Care Medicine*, 37(1), S69–S74.
- Asian Development Bank. (2010). *The informal sector and informal employment in Bangladesh*. Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/publications/informal-sector-and-informal-employment-bangladesh>
- Bairagya, I. (2010). *Liberalization, informal sector, and formal-informal sectors' relationship: A study of India*. Institute for Social and Economic Change.
- Banglapedia. (2021). Dalit community. *Banglapedia*. https://en.banglapedia.org/index.php/Dalit_Community
- Becker, M. (2012). Bagmusa – Dalit cobbler community. *The Advocacy Project*. <https://www.advocacynet.org/bagmusa-dalit-cobbler-community/>
- Boyce, C., & Neale, P. (2006). *Conducting in-depth interviews: A guide for designing and conducting in-depth interviews for evaluation input* (Vol. 2). Pathfinder International.
- Dallakoti, G. (2024, June 26). For shared prosperity, the formalization of work is vital. *The Daily Star*. <https://www.thedailystar.net/opinion/views/news/shared-prosperity-formalisation-work-vital-3642226>
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2011). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Etzold, B., & Mallick, B. (2015). Bangladesh: Country profile. Institute for Migration Research and Intercultural Studies (IMIS); Federal Agency for Civic Education.
- Farhat, N. (2020, October 17). Reopening the economy means little for a cobbler. *The Business Standard*. <https://www.tbsnews.net/coronavirus-chronicle/covid-19-bangladesh/reopening-economy-means-little-cobbler-146077>

- Fossey, E., Harvey, C., McDermott, F., & Davidson, L. (2002). Understanding and evaluating qualitative research. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 36(6), 717–732. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1440-1614.2002.01100.x>
- Green, J., & Thorogood, N. (2018). *Qualitative methods for health research* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Guest, G., MacQueen, K. M., & Namey, E. E. (2012). *Applied thematic analysis*. Sage.
- Guhathakurta, M., & Begum, S. (2022). From research to Dalit rights. *Academia.edu*. https://www.academia.edu/8326117/From_Research_to_Dalit_Rights
- Halder, S. R., & Urey, I. (2003). Changing food consumption patterns: Implications for nutrition and livelihoods.
- Hamid, M., & Jain, R. (2023). Socio-economic conditions of cobblers in Pune City. *South Asia Research*, 43(3), 417–432. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02627280231172410>
- History of the Cobbler. (n.d.). *The Shoe Healer*. <https://shoeh healer.co.uk/pages/history-of-the-cobbler>
- International Dalit Solidarity Network. (2024, April 15). *Homepage - International Dalit Solidarity Network*. <https://idsn.org/>
- Joffe, H. (2011). Thematic analysis. In D. Harper & A. R. Thompson (Eds.), *Qualitative research methods in mental health and psychotherapy: A guide for students and practitioners* (pp. 209–223). Wiley.
- Kamal, S., Khan, S., Islam, S., & Khan, R. (2010). *Dalits in Bangladesh: A study on deprivation*. Research and Development Collective (RDC). Manusher Jonno Foundation. <https://www.manusherjonno.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/DALIT-REPORT-for-Publication-from-RDC.pdf>
- Kaplan, A. (1964). *The conduct of inquiry: Methodology for behavioral science*. Harper & Row.
- Kelly, S. E., Bourgeault, I., & Dingwall, R. (2010). Qualitative interviewing techniques and styles. In I. Bourgeault, R. Dingwall, & R. de Vries (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of qualitative methods in health research* (pp. 307–326). Sage.
- Martin, C. A., Jenkins, D. R., Minhas, J. S., Gray, L. J., Tang, J., Williams, C., ... Pareek, M. (2020). Socio-demographic heterogeneity in the prevalence of COVID-19 during lockdown is associated with ethnicity and household size: Results from an observational cohort study. *EClinicalMedicine*, 25, 100466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100466>
- Mohajan, H. (2013). Economic development of Bangladesh. *Journal of Business Management and Administration*, 1(4), 41–48. <https://mpr a.ub.uni-muenchen.de/50663/>
- Mondal, B. K. (2015, June 11). A report on the lifestyle of the Rishi/Cobbler/Muchi community of Satkhira District. <https://socialscienc.blogspot.com/2015/06/lifestyle-of-rishicobblermuch.html>
- Pal, T. (2011). Geography of urban cobblers (Muchi or shoemaker): An overview in Bolpur Town, West Bengal, India. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(3), 238.
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533–544.

- Pandey, D., & Vats, A. (2020). Prevalence of musculoskeletal problems among cobblers in footwear repairing work. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 39(48), 68–72. <https://doi.org/10.9734/cjast/2020/v39i4831200>
- Popay, J., Rogers, A., & Williams, G. (1998). Rationale and standards for the systematic review of qualitative literature in health services research. *Qualitative Health Research*, 8(3), 341–351.
- Popping, R. (2015). Analyzing open-ended questions employing text analysis procedures. *Bulletin of Sociological Methodology/Bulletin de Méthodologie Sociologique*, 128(1), 23–39. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0759106315597389>
- Rutledge, P. B., & Hogg, J. L. C. (2020). In-depth interviews. *The International Encyclopedia of Media Psychology*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119011071.iemp0019>
- Saha, P., & Paul, R. N. (2003). The socio-economic situation of the cobbler community (an untouchable class of our society) in Dhaka City: An overview. *Self-Help Association for Rural People through Education and Entrepreneurship*. <https://www.dalits.nl/pdf/CobblerCommunity.pdf>
- Saktar, R., & Halder, R. (2023). Socio-economic conditions of Rishi community in Khulna City Corporation (KCC). *Indonesian Journal of Social Sciences*, 15(1), 40–48.
- Thabane, L., Ma, J., Chu, R., Cheng, J., Ismaila, A., Rios, L. P., ... & Goldsmith, C. H. (2010). A tutorial on pilot studies: What, why, and how. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 10(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-1>
- Toppo, A., Rahman, M. R., Ali, M. Y., & Javed, A. (2016). Socio-economic condition of plain land tribal people in Bangladesh. *Social Sciences*, 5(4), 58–63. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ss.20160504.12>
- Tribal Research & Cultural Institute, Tripura. (2020, November 20). *Socio-economic survey of the cobbler communities of Agartala Municipality*. Tribal Research & Cultural Institute.
- Ugwu, C. N., & Eze, V. H. U. (2023). Qualitative research. *IDOSR Journal of Computer and Applied Sciences*, 8(1), 20–35.
- Yeasin, H. M. (2022). Informal sector and economic growth in Bangladesh. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Applied and Basic Subjects*, 1(12), 48–61.
- Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods* (5th ed.). Sage.